

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Varberg, Wreck 1, Sweden

by

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Twenty samples from a wreck found during excavations at Varberg, Sweden, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. This wreck has been given the designation 'Varberg 1'. The result of the analysis is described in this report.

Varberg 1, Varberg

Nine samples are from planks from the ship, all *Quercus sp.*, oak. Three other samples are also oak, two from keel timbers and one from a floor. The remaining eight samples are all identified as pine (*Pinus sp.*). These are from frames, two stringers and a knee. All the oak samples are dated, but none of the pine could be dated.

Fig. 1. Varberg 1, shipwreck, Varberg, Sweden. The chronological position of the dated samples.

The oak planks are almost all radially converted from the parent tree. They are also all from very mature trees, where most plank samples contain between 180 to 250 tree-rings. Sapwood is preserved on five of the plank samples (see catalogue and fig. 1). One of these, sample 1061 (Z321001a) has the bark edge preserved. This sample is from a tree felled in winter 1471-72. Given the homogeneity of the planks from the ship (see provenance below), we might suggest that the trees for the planks were felled at the same time, in winter 1471-72 (highlighted with yellow in fig. 1).

The samples from the two keel timbers are, in contrast to the planks, from much younger trees. The forward keel timber, 1129, has pith and sapwood preserved, and contains only 98 tree-rings. This is dated. It is from a tree felled around AD 1470-85. The aft keel timber, 1130, also has sapwood and pith preserved, and this one contains only 83 tree-rings. It is from a tree felled around AD 1468-83. The two keel timbers can have been felled at the same time. The felling estimate for the keel timbers fall around the precise felling date for the planks, but given that they demonstrate a different timber source (see provenance below) they can have been felled later than the trees for the planks.

The oak floor timber, 1024, is also from a relatively young tree. This has pith and sapwood to bark edge preserved and contains 94 tree-rings, so was only a c. 100-year-old tree when it was felled. It is dated. This floor timber is from a tree felled in winter 1473-74 (marked with blue in fig. 1). If this is a repair/addition to the ship, this repair took place very shortly after the ship was built.

	Z321008a 1070	Z321005a 1113	Z321007a 1097	Z321003a 1081	Z321004a 1125	Z321009a 1089	Z321006a 1103	Z321001a 1061	Z321002a 1053	Z3210139 1024	Z3210149 1129	Z3210159 1130	
planks average Z321M004	Z321008a 1070	*	4.23	6.05	5.56	2.29	1.81	1.54	1.49	2.99	0.82	1.19	1.32
	Z321005a 1113	4.23*		6.24	5.71	6.62	3.77	4.91	4.49	4.21	0.69-		0.19
	Z321007a 1097	6.05	6.24*		7.65	5.85	3.65	4.19	3.49	4.6	1.34	2.78	1.3
	Z321003a 1081	5.56	5.71	7.65*		7.37	5.28	6.95	4.67	6.17	0.82	1.25	3.26
	Z321004a 1125	2.29	6.62	5.85	7.37*		5.91	7.57	4.57	4.89	1.28	0.48	1.7
	Z321009a 1089	1.81	3.77	3.65	5.28	5.91*		8.54	5.9	6.31	1.37	0.39	1.66
	Z321006a 1103	1.54	4.91	4.19	6.95	7.57	8.54*		9.01	8.51	1.04-		1.32
	Z321001a 1061	1.49	4.49	3.49	4.67	4.57	5.9	9.01*		7.85	0.84	0.35-	
	Z321002a 1053	2.99	4.21	4.6	6.17	4.89	6.31	8.51	7.85*		2.70	2.17	2.43
keels & floor average Z321M002	Z3210139 1024	0.82	0.69	1.34	0.82	1.28	1.37	1.04	0.84	2.70*		6.32	4.93
	Z3210149 1129	1.19-		2.78	1.25	0.48	0.39-		0.35	2.17	6.32*		6.13
	Z3210159 1130	1.32	0.19	1.3	3.26	1.7	1.66	1.32-		2.43	4.93	6.13*	

Table 1. Varberg wreck 1, Sweden. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) between the tree-ring curves from each dated sample with each other.

It has not been possible to date the pine samples from this ship. They are characterized by very knotty wood and many of the samples have very abrupt changes in their tree-ring patterns, indicating highly fluctuating growth conditions, during their growth. Only three samples contain more than 100 tree-rings, but these do not display correlation with each other, and it has not been possible to find a date for them.

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Filenames	-	-	planks Z321M004	
-	start	dates	AD1208	
-	dates	end	AD1471	
Master and site chronologies				
klaiped	AD1260	AD1536	9.95	Lithuania, Klaipeda (Vitas 2020)
jkdM1&2	AD1272	AD1479	8.79	Latvia, Riga, church door, 2 timbers (Zunde pers comm)
SJM1	AD1284	AD1490	8.63	Latvia, Riga, St Jakobs Church, 3 timbers (Daly & Zunde unpubl)
SJM2	AD1342	AD1514	7.45	Latvia, Riga, St Jakobs Church, 12 timbers (Daly & Zunde unpubl)
Chronologies from artworks				
21BLT1B	AD1181	AD1527	14.66	Painted panels Baltic1 Bowhill-Vejdyb type 81 trees (Daly & Tyers 2022)
Z268M002	AD1215	AD1515	11.46	Norway, Ringsaker church, altarpiece, 4 timbers (Daly 2019c)
2021BLT1	AD1143	AD1626	11.20	Painted panels Baltic1, 552 trees (Daly & Tyers 2022)
Z278M001	AD1366	AD1496	9.04	Norway, Kinn church, altarpiece, planks 2 timbers (Daly 2020)
Z256M001	AD1239	AD1479	7.96	Norway, Missale Nidrosiense, book binding, 5 timbers (Daly 2019b)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	7.34	Scotland, Stirling Castle, heads Baltic oak (Crone pers comm)
Chronologies from ships				
Z2261M03	AD1264	AD1537	13.39	Denmark, Køge 2, shipwreck, double planks, 7 timbers (Daly 2019a)
Z2261M01	AD1098	AD1522	10.69	Denmark, Køge 2, shipwreck, planks, 18 timbers (Daly 2019a)
00751M01	AD1113	AD1463	8.95	Denmark, Vejdyb shipwreck, 14 trees (Daly 1997)
Z054m001	AD1235	AD1448	7.69	Germany, shipwreck, Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92, planks, 5 timbers (Daly 2010)

Table 2. Varberg wreck 1, Sweden. Result of the correlation between the average for the oak planks from the ship (Z321M004) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	keels & floor Z321M002	
-	start	dates	AD1367	
-	dates	end	AD1473	
Master and site chronologies				
D0134M03	AD1347	AD1507	5.02	Denmark, Odense, Thomas B Thriges, bridge, 6 timbers (Daly 2017)
H030M004	AD1296	AD1517	4.99	Denmark, Aalborg, Nytorv, 7 timbers late group (Daly 2022)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	4.75	Southern Scandinavia, 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	4.54	Denmark, Sjælland, 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	4.33	Denmark, Ålborg, Østerå & Boulevarden, 67 timbers (Daly 2000 2001)
B012M001	AD1347	AD1484	4.27	Denmark, Copenhagen, Admiralgade, 3 timbers (Daly 2005)
Chronologies from southern Scandinavian exports				
Ep3mnall	AD1361	AD1539	5.35	Scotland, Stirling Castle, episode 3 (Crone pers comm)
EP21505	AD1355	AD1505	4.73	Scotland, Stirling Castle, episode 2 (Crone pers comm)
Chronologies from ships				
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	4.66	Sweden, Göteborg, Klippan 2 shipwreck, 11 timbers (Daly 2015)
WSshipsM01	AD1352	AD1636	4.25	West Swedish ships, 29 timbers (Daly unpubl)

Table 3. Varberg wreck 1, Sweden. Result of the correlation between the average for the two keel timbers and the single oak frame from the ship (Z321M002) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Provenance

The dated oak samples from Varberg 1 correlate with each other as shown in table 1. Highly significant agreement appears between the tree-ring curves from the nine plank samples (highlighted with yellow) and an average of these (Z321M004) is calculated. This average is 264 years in length and covers the period AD 1208-1471. The correlations (t -value) between this average and a range of tree-ring

datasets for Northern Europe are shown in table 2. The plank average is dating against a wide range of oak tree-ring datasets derived from dendrochronological analysis of painted panels that were made in western Europe (chiefly in the low countries) from oak imported from the south and east Baltic region. The Varberg 1 planks correlate best with the so-called Baltic 1 group from artworks (see Daly & Tyers 2022). The hull planking for the ship Varberg 1 most probably represents transport of oak planking from the region of Lithuania. The other three timbers from the ship (the two keel timbers and the oak floor) do not correlate with the planking, but they do display good agreement with each other (table 1, highlighted with blue). An average of these three is calculated, Z321M002, of 107 years in length. This average covers the period AD 1367-1473. This is dating with tree-ring datasets for southern Scandinavia, achieving highest correlations with Danish sites and with timbers from Scotland that have been shown to derive from southern Scandinavian exports (table 3). While the correlation values are not high enough to allow us to pinpoint the precise provenance of these oaks, due to the relatively short series and low replication, it does point us in the direction of south Scandinavia for this group. As the ship also incorporates extensive use of pine for the frames, the building of the ship at a Scandinavian site can be suggested.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted. For estimating the felling date of the trees several sapwood statistics are considered. For oaks in northern Poland we apply 15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990) while there is a shorter estimate in Estonia/South Finland, just 12 (-6+7) sapwood rings (Sohar et al 2012). I have here chosen a median of these two, calculating 13 (-6+8) or 7 to 21 sapwood years when estimating the felling date of the trees for the oak planks from the ship. For the two keel timbers a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used for estimating the felling date of these. This is a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Norway (c. 15 sapwood years (-8+6)) (Christensen & Havemann 1998).

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Samples											
Z321001a 106	Varberg I 1061 plank QUSP	206	AD1266	AD1471	G	15	W	T	N	1.16	AD1471-72 winter
Z321002a 105	Varberg I 1053 plank QUSP	214	AD1237	AD1450	G	11	N	R	S1	1.31	AD1451-63
Z321003a 108	Varberg I 1081 plank QUSP	186	AD1251	AD1436	G	0	N	R	H1	1.39	after AD1444
Z321004a 112	Varberg I 1125 plank QUSP	180	AD1288	AD1467	G	11	N	R	S1	1.42	AD1468-77
Z321005a 111	Varberg I 1113 plank QUSP	250	AD1208	AD1457	G	0	N	R	H1	1.01	after AD1465
Z321006a 110	Varberg I 1103 plank QUSP	139	AD1326	AD1464	G	4	N	R	S1	1.83	AD1467-81
Z321007a 109	Varberg I 1097 plank QUSP	185	AD1230	AD1414	G	0	N	R	H1	1.33	after AD1422
Z321008a 107	Varberg I 1070 plank QUSP	211	AD1213	AD1423	G	0	N	T	N	1.14	after AD1430
Z321009a 108	Varberg I 1089 plank QUSP	181	AD1284	AD1464	G	7	N	R	N	1.35	AD1464-78
Z321010a	Varberg I 1020 frame floor PISY	69			C	17	W	O	N	3.96	undated
Z321011a	Varberg I 1027 frame floor PISY	106			C	0	N	S	H1	1.70	undated
Z321012a	Varberg I 1019 frame floor PISY	148			C	60	N	H	N	1.27	undated
Z3210139 102	Varberg I 1024 frame floor QUSP	94	AD1380	AD1473	C	8	W	S	N	1.14	AD1473-74 winter
Z3210149 112	Varberg I 1129 keel fore QUSP	98	AD1367	AD1464	C	4	N	O	S1	1.93	AD1470-85
Z3210159 113	Varberg I 1130 keel aft QUSP	83	AD1382	AD1464	C	6	N	O	S1	1.45	AD1468-83
Z321016a	Varberg I 1022 frame floor PISY	34			F	10	W	O	N	6.19	undated
Z321017a	Varberg I 1002 knee PISY	117			C	56	N	S	S1	0.78	undated
Z321018a	Varberg I 1001 vögare PISY	77			C	22	N	S	N	1.79	undated
Z321019a	Varberg I 1016 vögare PISY	71			C	30	N	S	N	1.26	undated
Not measured	Varberg I 1023 frame floor PISY	c. 40									undated
Averages											
Z321M002	Varberg I frame & keels 3 timbers QUSP	107	AD1367	AD1473						1.69	
Z321M004	Varberg I planks 9 timbers QUSP	264	AD1208	AD1471						1.28	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies sp.</i> , fir.											
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